

REQUEST FOR EXCHANGE OF INFORMATION

REQUEST DETAILS	
Requesting institution	Federal German Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR)
Country	Germany
Date of request	19/02/2021
Request Number select from excel file	171
Title of request	Request for information on production and trade of fresh produce in Europe for One Health EJP TOXOSOURCES project
Description of request (including background)	<p>TOXOSOURCES (<i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> sources quantified; https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-toxosources/) is a Joint Research Project within the H2020 One Health European Joint Programme (https://onehealthjep.eu/) with funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (Grant Agreement No 773830).</p> <p>TOXOSOURCES aims to address the research question – What are the relative contributions of the different sources of <i>T. gondii</i> infection? – following research needs identified by ECDC and EFSA. <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> is a highly prioritized zoonotic foodborne parasite but is so far not systematically controlled in Europe and globally. Meat is considered an important source of <i>T. gondii</i> infections. Consumption of contaminated fresh produce is one of the possible routes of <i>T. gondii</i> transmission to humans, which has been little explored to date. TOXOSOURCES project investigates the role of ready-to-eat fresh produce that is intended to be eaten raw (fourth range products) as well as the role of meat as sources of <i>T. gondii</i> infection.</p> <p>As part of TOXOSOURCES work packages 2 and 3, we are gathering data on the trade and consumption of fresh produce/vegetables and</p>

meat within the European Economic Area. The data will be used to evaluate the possible role of fresh produce and meat as sources of *T. gondii* infection (quantitative microbiological risk assessment), and taken into account in designing sampling for a multi-centre study investigating selected fresh produce for presence of *T. gondii* oocysts.

We kindly request the following information from EFSA focal points:

- 1) In relation to the following ready-to-eat salad products:
 - Arugula/rocket
 - Brassicas: kale, cabbage, Chinese cabbage, collard greens
 - Chard
 - Chicory/escarole
 - Endive
 - Lettuce: romaine, leaf red or green
 - Spinach
 - Cress, watercress
 - All ready-to-eat salad products
 - a) Annual production in their country (in tonnes per year) for the years 2018 and 2019. Please indicate total production, and if the data are available, production depending on production type (open field vs greenhouse, organic vs non-organic) and on holding size (small-scale producers vs large scale producers).
 - b) Annual imports into their country from the European Economic Area (EEA) or third countries. Please indicate country(ies) of origin and quantity imported per country (in tonnes per year) for the following ready-to-eat salad products for the years 2018 and 2019.
 - c) Annual exports from their country to the EEA or third countries. Please indicate country(ies) exported to and quantity exported to each country (in tonnes per year for the years 2018 and 2019
 - d) Annual consumption in their country (in tonnes per year) for the years 2018 and 2019
- 2) In relation to the following meat products:
 - Fresh meat cuts: beef/veal e.g. steaks, roasts, chops
 - Fresh meat cuts: pork e.g. loin, chops
 - Fresh meat cuts: poultry e.g. breast, drumstick, wing, fillet from chicken, turkey, duck, goose, ratitis (ostrich)
 - Fresh meat cuts: lamb (sheep or goat) e.g. saddle, shoulder, neck, leg

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fresh meat cuts: mutton or goat e.g. loin, chops, fillet steak • Fresh meat cuts: horse • Fresh meat cuts: game (mammals) e.g. deer, wild boar, moose, elk, hare, mouflon, chamois, ibex • Fresh meat cuts: wild birds e.g. goose, pheasant, grouse, pigeon, partridge, quail, guineafowl, wild duck, wild goose • Fresh minced/ground meat products: beef/veal e.g. burgers, meatballs, meatloaf • Fresh minced/ground meat products: pork e.g. patties, meatballs, meatloaf • Fresh minced/ground meat products: mixed beef/pork e.g. patties, meatballs, meatloaf • Fresh sausages (all species) e.g. chipolata-type sausage, fresh bratwurst, fresh raw sausages, fresh spiced sausages in casing, breakfast-type sausage • Dry-fermented sausages e.g. salami, chorizo • Raw cured pork meat e.g. raw ham, bacon, pancetta • Raw cured beef e.g. smoked beef <p>a) Quantity sold fresh/raw (i.e. unfrozen) in their country in the years 2018 and 2019.</p> <p>b) Quantity of the following sold fresh/raw (i.e. unfrozen) in their country in the years 2018 and 2019 which was frozen prior to sale.</p> <p>c) Quantity sold frozen in their country in the years 2018 and 2019.</p> <p>d) Quantity sold fresh/raw in their country in the years 2018 and 2019 that was imported from EEA or third countries</p>
Deadline for submission of replies	15th March 2021
Remit(s) of request More than one option can be listed	Biological hazards (BIOHAZ) Contaminants (CONTAM) Other area falling within EFSA's remit: Food safety
Request concern(s)	Risk assessment
Title(s) or link(s) to background document(s)	https://onehealthjp.eu/jrp-toxosources/

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¹ *This designation is without prejudice to positions on status and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.*

REPLYING COUNTRY: Albania

Replying Institution	
Date of reply	DD/MM/YYYY
Title(s) or link(s) to background document(s)	

REPLYING COUNTRY: Austria

Replying Institution	AGES GmbH – Risk Assessment
Date of reply	12/02/2021
<p>The information on production and trade can be found on http://www.statistik.at/web_en/statistics/Economy/agriculture_and_forestry/prices_balances/supply_balance_sheets/index.html</p> <p>We have attached the most relevant tables regarding the balance sheets for meat and vegetables. If you need more details, please contact info@statistik.gv.at.</p>	
Title(s) or link(s) to background document(s)	EXCEL file: supply_balance_sheet_for_meat_by_species_2014_to_2019 supply_balance_sheet_for_vegetables_201314_to_201819 --> saved under Requests for Exchange of Information / files / 171_DE_One Health EJP TOXOSOURCES project

Title(s) or link(s) to background document(s)	EXCEL file: https://teams.microsoft.com/l/file/DAA9FBC4-8C4F-4384-9162-94CD2669C1B7?tenantId=406a174b-e315-48bd-aa0a-cdaddc44250b&fileType=xlsx&objectUrl=https%3A%2F%2Fefsa815.sharepoint.com%2Fsites%2FfocalPointsNetwork%2FShared%20Documents%2FRequests%20for%20Exchange%20of%20Information%2F2021%2F171_DE_OneHealth-EJP-Toxosources-project_EXCEL_Austria%2FAnnual%20production%20in%20the%20Republic%20of%20Croatia_2018_2019.xlsx&baseurl=https%3A%2F%2Fefsa815.sharepoint.com%2Fsites%2FfocalPointsNetwork&serviceName=teams&threadId=19:28d8d72b74f5480f83cea1388e532b5e@thread.skype&groupId=2b501c25-26c2-4cf4-a179-2999b6d5c3a5
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REPLYING COUNTRY: Cyprus	
Replying Institution	
Date of reply	DD/MM/YYYY
Title(s) or link(s) to background document(s)	

REPLYING COUNTRY: Czech Republic	
Replying Institution	Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic
Date of reply	15/03/2021

Only some data is available in the Czech Republic. The Excel file was uploaded in the respective TEAMS folder: https://teams.microsoft.com/_#/files/Requests%20for%20Exchange%20of%20Information?threadId=19%3A28d8d72b74f5480f83cea1388e532b5e%40thread.skype&replyChainId=1614346779494&ctx=channel&context=171_DE_OneHealth-EJP-Toxosources-project_EXCEL_Austria&rootfolder=%252Fsites%252FFocalPointsNetwork%252FShared%2520Documents%252FRequests%2520for%2520Exchange%2520of%2520Information%252F2021%252F171_DE_OneHealth-EJP-Toxosources-project_EXCEL_Austria

Title(s) or link(s) to background document(s)

REPLYING COUNTRY: Denmark

Replying Institution

Date of reply

DD/MM/YYYY

Title(s) or link(s) to background document(s)

REPLYING COUNTRY: Estonia

Replying Institution

Date of reply

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Title(s) or link(s) to background document(s)	

REPLYING COUNTRY: Finland	
Replying Institution	
Date of reply	DD/MM/YYYY
Title(s) or link(s) to background document(s)	

REPLYING COUNTRY: France	
Replying Institution	
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REPLYING COUNTRY: Germany	
Replying Institution	
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REPLYING COUNTRY: Greece	
Replying Institution	
Date of reply	DD/MM/YYYY

Title(s) or link(s) to background document(s)	

REPLYING COUNTRY: Hungary

Replying Institution	National Food Chain Safety Office
Date of reply	15/03/2021
<p>Our response, in the form of an Excel table has been uploaded into the request file folder in TEAMS.</p>	
Title(s) or link(s) to background document(s)	

REPLYING COUNTRY: Iceland

Replying Institution	
Date of reply	DD/MM/YYYY

Title(s) or link(s) to background document(s)	

REPLYING COUNTRY: Ireland

Replying Institution	Food Safety Authority of Ireland
Date of reply	16/03/2021
<p>Please find below links to relevant information on export/import of some meat and vegetable products and food consumption:</p> <p>https://www.cso.ie/en/releasesandpublications/ep/p-ti/irelandstradinggoods2018/</p> <p>https://www.cso.ie/en/releasesandpublications/ep/p-ti/irelandstradinggoods2017/food2017/</p> <p>https://www.bordbia.ie/globalassets/bordbia.ie/about/governance/annual-reports-pdfs/annual-report-2018.pdf</p> <p>https://www.bordbia.ie/globalassets/bordbia.ie/about/governance/annual-reports-pdfs/bord-bia-annual-report-2019.pdf</p> <p>https://irp-cdn.multiscreensite.com/46a7ad27/files/uploaded/The%20National%20Adult%20Nutrition%20Survey%20Summary%20Report%20March%202011.pdf</p>	
Title(s) or link(s) to background document(s)	

REPLYING COUNTRY: Italy

Replying Institution	
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Date of reply	DD/MM/YYYY
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REPLYING COUNTRY: Kosovo

Replying Institution	
Date of reply	DD/MM/YYYY
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REPLYING COUNTRY: Latvia

Replying Institution	
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Date of reply	DD/MM/YYYY
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REPLYING COUNTRY: Lithuania

Replying Institution	State Food and Veterinary Service
Date of reply	01/03/2021

The following information available to the State Food and Veterinary Service:

1 a)

Production in Lithuania	Quantity in tons per year	
	2018	2019
Cabbage	54480	59742
Lettuce	1597	1016
Spinach	123	590

1 b)

No import of fresh lettuce.

Import of cabbage:

Country of origin	Quantity in tons per year	
	2018	2019
Albania	235	384
North Macedonia	1210	2825
Belarus	37	400
Russia	0	118

2 d)

Country of origin / imported production	Quantity in tons per year	
	2018	2019
Ukraine / Poultry meat and poultry meat products	572	517

Title(s) or link(s) to background document(s)	
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REPLYING COUNTRY: Luxembourg

Replying Institution	
Date of reply	DD/MM/YYYY
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REPLYING COUNTRY: Malta

Replying Institution	
Date of reply	DD/MM/YYYY

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REPLYING COUNTRY: Montenegro

Replying Institution	
Date of reply	DD/MM/YYYY
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REPLYING COUNTRY: North Macedonia

Replying Institution	
Date of reply	DD/MM/YYYY

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REPLYING COUNTRY: Norway

Replying Institution	
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REPLYING COUNTRY: Poland

Replying Institution	
Date of reply	DD/MM/YYYY

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REPLYING COUNTRY: Portugal

Replying Institution	Directorate General for Food and Veterinary (DGAV); Statistics of Portugal (INE)
Date of reply	09/03/2021

Referring to the information made available by the Statistics Portugal (INE- Instituto Nacional de Estatística), the Directorate-General for Food and Veterinary (DGAV) provided the following response:

In order to be able to obtain this information, the products in question were related to the CN (Combined Nomenclature) codes

Product	CN code
Arugula/rocket	incluído no 0705
Brassicac: kale, cabbage, Chinese cabbage, collard greens (Couves, couve-flor, repolho ou couve frisada, couve-rábano e produtos comestíveis semelhantes do género Brassica, frescos ou refrigerados)	0704
Chard (Rama da beterraba, Beta vulgaris subsp. vulgaris)	
Chicory/escarole	incluído no 0705
Endive	incluído no 0705
Lettuce: romaine, leaf red or green (Alfases (Lactuca sativa) e chicórias (Cichorium spp.), frescas ou refrigeradas)	0705
Spinach (Espinafres, espinafres-da-nova-zelândia e espinafres gigantes)	0709 70 00
Cress, watercress	07099990
All ready-to-eat salad products: (Saladas, excepto alfases (Lactuca sativa) e chicórias (Cichorium spp.))	0709 99 10
Outros produtos hortícolas preparados ou conservados, excepto em vinagre ou em ácido acético, congelados, com excepção dos produtos da posição 2006	2004
Outros produtos hortícolas preparados ou conservados, excepto em vinagre ou em ácido acético, congelados, com excepção dos produtos da posição 2006	2005
Cortes de carne fresca: carne de bovino , por exemplo bifes, assados, costeletas	0201 (0201.30.00)
Cortes de carne fresca: porco , por ex. lombo, costeletas	0203 (0203,.19.13)
Cortes de carne fresca: aves , por ex. peito, coxinha, asa, filé de frango, peru, pato, ganso, ratitis (avestruz)	0207 (0207.13)
Cortes de carne fresca: cordeiro (ovelha ou cabra) , por ex. sela, ombro, pescoço, perna	0204
Cortes de carne fresca: carneiro ou cabra , por ex. lombo, costeletas, bife de filé	0204
Cortes de carne fresca: cavalo	0205.00.20
Cortes de carne fresca: caça (mamíferos), por ex. veado, javali, alce, alce, lebre, muflão, camurça, ibex	0208 (0208.90.30)
Cortes de carne fresca: aves selvagens, por ex. ganso, faisão, perdiz, pombo, perdiz, codorna, guineafowl, pato selvagem, ganso selvagem	0207.54
Produtos de carne fresca picada / moída: carne de bovino , por exemplo hambúrgueres, almôndegas, bolo de carne	0201.30.00

Produtos de carne fresca picada / moída: carne de porco , por exemplo rissóis, almôndegas, bolo de carne	0203.19.55
Produtos de carne fresca picada / moída: mistura de carne bovina / suína , por exemplo rissóis, almôndegas, bolo de carne	
Salsichas frescas (todas as espécies), por ex. salsicha tipo chipolata, bratwurst fresca, linguiça crua fresca, linguiça fresca com tempero, linguiça tipo café da manhã	1601.00
Salsichas fermentadas a seco, por ex. salame, chouriço	0210
Carne de porco curada crua, por ex. presunto cru, bacon, pancetta	0210
Carne crua curada, por ex. Carne defumada	0210

- The Excel file presents the import and export data of fresh produce 2018-2019. In the sheet "2018_2019_8_DIGITOS", information has been included with the maximum level of the Combined Nomenclature (8 digits), for all codes belonging to the CN positions, 0201, 0203, 0204, 0207, 0208, 0210, 0704, 0705, 1601, 2004 and 2005, in case you need additional information on other goods;
- links to information available at INE regarding consumption:
 1. [Grau de auto-abastecimento de hortícolas \(%\) por Espécie de produtos hortícolas \(Balanços de mercado\); Anual](#)
 2. [Consumo humano de hortícolas per capita \(kg/ hab.\) por Espécie de produtos hortícolas \(Balanços de mercado\); Anual](#)
 3. [Consumo humano de hortícolas \(t\) por Espécie de produtos hortícolas \(Balanços de mercado\); Anual](#)
 4. [Grau de auto-abastecimento de hortícolas \(%\); Anual](#)
 5. [Consumo humano de hortícolas per capita \(kg/ hab.\); Anual](#)
 6. [Consumo humano de hortícolas \(t\); Anual](#)
- links to information available at INE on the production of these products: [Área, produção e produtividade das principais culturas](#)

Title(s) or link(s) to background document(s)

REPLYING COUNTRY: Romania

Replying Institution

Date of reply

DD/MM/YYYY

Title(s) or link(s) to background document(s)	

REPLYING COUNTRY: Serbia	
Replying Institution	
Date of reply	DD/MM/YYYY
Title(s) or link(s) to background document(s)	

REPLYING COUNTRY: Slovak Republic	
Replying Institution	Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development of the Slovak Republic
Date of reply	15/03/2021

Data about the production of chosen products (*where the data are available*) in the Slovak republic:

- ***Kale, cabbage, Chinese cabbage, collard greens***
2018: 14976 tonnes (t)
2019: 13 882 t
- ***Spinach***
2018: 870 t
2019: 988 t
- ***All ready-to-eat salad products***
2018: 180 t
2019: 67 t

Data about the type of production as well the holding size of the producers are not available.

Data regarding the export and import of vegetables and meat are uploaded as the xls. files in the Slovak language in [this folder](#).

Title(s) or link(s) to background document(s)	
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REPLYING COUNTRY: Slovenia

Replying Institution	
Date of reply	DD/MM/YYYY
Title(s) or link(s) to background document(s)	

REPLYING COUNTRY: Spain

Replying Institution	Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food
Date of reply	08/03/2021

1) At present Spain does not have processed data on these specific products, but we can provide the sources we usually consult to obtain such data:

a) **Annual production for 2018 and 2019** (total and distinguishing, if possible, between **open field and greenhouse** and between **organic and non-organic**, as well as the **holding size**):

i. **Data on the production (open field vs greenhouse)** can be found here:

<https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadisticas-agrarias/agricultura/superficies-producciones-anuales-cultivos/>. More specifically, under “**Hortalizas**” (vegetables) which include most of the products and years related to this request.

ii. **Data on the organic/non-organic production** of these products can be found here: [La Producción Ecológica \(mapa.gob.es\)](http://La Producción Ecológica (mapa.gob.es)). The **annual reports** include charts for the years 2018 and 2019.

iii. There is no **data on the holding size** because, generally, this information comes from the technical economic focus (OTE) and comprises all horticulture. Therefore, the data obtained will not be representative of the intended subsector.

b) **Annual imports in Spain from EEA and Third Countries indicating country of origin and quantity of the ready-to-eat salad products for 2018 and 2019.**

Regarding Foreign Trade, we work with the EUROSTAT Easy Comext: [Dimension Selection \(europa.eu\)](http://Dimension Selection (europa.eu)), to obtain information entering the TARIC for the identified products (some are included in groups and it is not possible to identify them individually):

- Arugula/rocket – **NO TARIC AVAILABLE**
- Brassicas: kale, cabbage, Chinese cabbage, collard greens – **TARIC 0704**
- Chard – **NO TARIC AVAILABLE**
- Chicory/escarole – **TARIC 070529**
- Endive – **TARIC 070521**
- Lettuce: romaine, leaf red or green – **TARIC 070511 AND 070519**
- Spinach – **TARIC 070910**
- Cress, watercress – **NO TARIC AVAILABLE**
- All ready-to-eat salad products – **NO TARIC AVAILABLE**

c) **Annual exports in Spain from EEA and Third Countries indicating country of origin and quantity of the ready-to-eat salad products for 2018 and 2019.**

Same as with imports but selecting the flow of the exports.

d) **Annual consumption in Spain for 2018 and 2019.**

The only information available at the moment concerns the **National Household Consumption** and can be consulted here: [Series anuales \(mapa.gob.es\)](http://Series anuales (mapa.gob.es)). The information on several of the requested products can be found there, including fresh-cut vegetables.

2. In relation to meat products, you can check the following reports.

https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/alimentacion/temas/consumo-tendencias/20190624_informedeconsumo2018pdf_tcm30-510816.pdf

https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/alimentacion/temas/consumo-tendencias/informe2019_v2_tcm30-540250.pdf

Notice that these reports also include information about all kind of food consumption trends.

Title(s) or link(s) to background document(s)	
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REPLYING COUNTRY: Sweden

Replying Institution	
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Date of reply	
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REPLYING COUNTRY: Switzerland

Replying Institution	
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Date of reply	
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Title(s) or link(s) to background document(s)	

REPLYING COUNTRY: The Netherlands

Replying Institution	Netherlands Food and Consumer Product Safety Authority
Date of reply	15/03/2021
<p>Figures on production and trade of food crops and meat in The Netherlands can be found in several databases:</p> <p>Statline Database of Statistics Netherlands (CBS): https://opendata.cbs.nl/statline/#/CBS/en/navigatieScherm/thema?themaNr=81650</p> <p>Agro & food portal from Wageningen University & Research (WUR): https://www.agrimatie.nl/Default.aspx?subpubID=2232</p> <p>Information on food consumption in The Netherlands can be found on the website of the National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM) https://www.rivm.nl/en/dutch-national-food-consumption-survey</p>	
Title(s) or link(s) to background document(s)	https://opendata.cbs.nl/statline/#/CBS/en/navigatieScherm/thema?themaNr=81650 https://www.agrimatie.nl/Default.aspx?subpubID=2232 https://www.rivm.nl/en/dutch-national-food-consumption-survey

REPLYING COUNTRY: Turkey

Replying Institution	
Date of reply	DD/MM/YYYY

Title(s) or link(s) to background document(s)	

REPLYING COUNTRY: United Kingdom	
Replying Institution	
Date of reply	DD/MM/YYYY
Title(s) or link(s) to background document(s)	